

The Rare Disease Achalasia & Digital Innovation: Contrasting Computed Tomography-based & In-house 3D Reconstructions of the Esophagus for Accuracy Assessment

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Abstract Achalasia, a rare esophageal disorder, requires precise 3D models to improve treatment. This study validates the *Esophagus Visualization* software, a platform that reconstructs patient-specific esophageal models from multi-modal data (TBE, EGD, HRM), by comparing them to CT-derived ground truth in a six-patient cohort. The best reconstruction, using comprehensive multi-modal inputs, showed a mean geometric deviation of 0.293 cm and a volumetric difference under 10 cm³. Reconstructions based only on TBE data showed more variability (mean deviations of 0.301 to 0.544 cm), largely due to assumptions of circular cross-sections and differences in patient posture during imaging. These results confirm the software's potential for clinical accuracy, especially when EGD data is included, and support future development, such as generative AI for reconstructions using only EGD data.

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1 Introduction

Achalasia, a relatively uncommon but significant motility disorder of the esophagus, presents a clinical challenge characterized by fundamental impairment in the act of swallowing [1, 1]. Defined by inadequate relaxation of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) and the absence of effective esophageal peristalsis, this condition obstructs the passage of the ingesta, leading to considerable patient morbidity manifested through dysphagia, regurgitation, and potential long-term sequelae [1, 1]. Significant progress in understanding the functional pathophysiology of achalasia has been achieved over the past decades, principally through the advent of High-Resolution Manometry (HRM) and the subsequent development and refinement of the Chicago Classification system, currently in version 4.0 [2, 3] [3, 161]. Concurrently, therapeutic interventions have advanced, with minimally invasive techniques such as Peroral Endoscopic Myotomy (POEM) offering highly tailored approaches alongside established methods, such as Pneumatic Dilation and Laparoscopic Heller Myotomy [4, 53] [5, 330] [6, 1]. These diagnostic and therapeutic advancements highlight the increasing necessity for tools capable of comprehensively capturing patient-specific structural and functional characteristics of the disease to inform personalized treatment strategies for each patient.

Despite this emphasis on functional assessment and therapeutic efficacy, an accurate three-dimensional (3D) representation of the associated structural alterations within the achalasic esophagus remains a significant challenge. Standard diagnostic modalities such as HRM, Timed Barium Esophagram (TBE), and Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) each contribute valuable information but yield incomplete or lower-dimensional perspectives on complex esophageal anatomy and pathology [1, 14]. HRM provides detailed pressure dynamics but lacks direct anatomical correlation [1, 9]. TBE offers visualization of luminal morphology and emptying dynamics but is limited by its 2D projective nature and lack of wall detail [7, 7]. EGD allows direct mucosal inspection but provides only localized cross-sectional views that are inherently operator-dependent and subjective [8, 866]. Consequently, clinical interpretation necessitates the cognitive synthesis of these disparate data sources, an inherently subjective process that constrains the ability to precisely quantify anatomical changes or plan interventions that require detailed spatial information [1, 7]. Computational methodologies aimed at integrating multimodal data into unified 3D models, such as the in-house *Esophagus Visualization* software [9, 53] [10, 3], represent potential solutions. This system attempt to fuse TBE-derived contours, spatiotemporal HRM pressure data, and EGD-based cross-sections into a cohesive 3D esophageal representation [10, 8]. However, the anatomical fidelity of 3D models generated through such inferential, multimodal processes, particularly when relying heavily on 2D projections and functional data, necessitates rigorous quantitative assessment against a reliable structural benchmark. The extent to which these software-derived models accurately depict the true patient-specific 3D esophageal anatomy remains to be formally evaluated.

The primary objective of this study was to conduct a formal validation of the 3D esophageal reconstructions generated by our in-house *Esophagus Visualization* software. The central research question addressed is as follows:

To what degree of geometric and volumetric accuracy can the multi-modal software *Esophagus Visualization* reconstruct the 3D anatomy of the achalasia esophagus when compared against high-fidelity anatomical models derived from patients Computed Tomography scans?

Computed Tomography (CT) data were used as the anatomical ground truth reference standard owing to their intrinsic volumetric nature, superior spatial resolution, and established capability to depict detailed cross-sectional anatomy, thus providing a robust basis for structural comparison [11, 1207]. This study presents a comprehensive validation framework in which software-generated 3D meshes were systematically compared with the corresponding CT-derived models using established quantitative geometric metrics and comparative volumetric analyses. These quantitative measures were applied both globally to the entire esophagus and locally to functionally significant subregions (tubular esophagus and LES parts). Qualitative visual assessments conducted by domain experts provide complementary information. This validation effort, incorporating data from both direct clinical collaboration and public repositories (e.g., Radiopaedia.org [12]) while adhering to data quality management standards [13, 13], aims to objectively quantify the accuracy achievable by the *Esophagus Visualization* reconstruction approach. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides essential background information on achalasia and relevant 3D reconstruction methodologies. Section 3 details the procedures for data acquisition, ground truth generation, software model reconstruction, and the comparative validation methodology. Section 4 presents the quantitative results derived from this comparison. Section 5 discusses the implications, inherent limitations, and potential clinical utility of these findings. Finally, Section 6 offers concluding remarks regarding this study.

2 Background and Related Work

A comprehensive understanding of achalasia necessitates a firm grasp of both its underlying pathophysiology and the current landscape of diagnostic and reconstructive technologies. This section provides essential background on the clinical context of the achalasic esophagus and the standard modalities used in its assessment. Subsequently, it reviews methodologies pertinent to 3D esophageal reconstruction and introduces the core computational algorithms that provide the foundation for the validation framework presented in this study.

2.1 The Achalasic Esophagus: Anatomy, Function, and Clinical Context

Achalasia is a primary disorder of esophageal motility, fundamentally defined by the impairment of LES relaxation during swallowing, coupled with the absence of effective propagated peristaltic contractions within the esophageal body [1, 1]. This dual physiological impairment disrupts the normal, coordinated transport of ingested material from the pharynx to the stomach [3, 160]. Normally, swallowing initiates relaxation of both

the upper esophageal sphincter and the LES, followed by a sequential peristaltic wave that propels the bolus distally [1, 3]. In achalasia, failure of LES relaxation and loss of organized peristalsis lead to functional obstruction at the esophagogastric junction (EGJ) [1, 1].

The underlying pathophysiology involves progressive, immune-mediated destruction of inhibitory neurons within the myenteric plexus [1, 3]. This selective loss disrupts the crucial balance between excitatory and inhibitory neural control necessary for coordinated LES relaxation and peristalsis [1, 3]. The resulting motor dysfunction manifests differently depending on the stage and subtype of the disease, as defined by the Chicago Classification based on HRM findings [3, 161].

Figure 1: Pathophysiological Progression of Achalasia[1, 4]

Abbildung 1 from Savarino et al. [1, 4] visually encapsulates the natural history and pathophysiological progression of the disease. It contrasts the normal esophagus with its corresponding healthy myenteric plexus and ganglion cells, ensuring coordinated peristalsis and LES relaxation against the progressive stages of the disease. In Early achalasia, immune-mediated inflammation targets the myenteric plexus, initiating gradual neuronal destruction. While the loss of inhibitory innervation begins, symptoms may be non-specific or mimic gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), often delaying diagnosis. As the disease progresses to established achalasia there is significant depletion of the myenteric plexus and observable inflammation in the remaining ganglion cells. This results in characteristic impaired LES relaxation and abnormal or absent body peristalsis, leading to abnormal esophageal emptying and the classic symptoms of dysphagia, regurgitation, and weight loss. Esophageal dilation begins during this stage. In End-stage achalasia,

there is an extreme loss of the myenteric plexus, with destroyed and fibrosed ganglion cells. This results in a severely dilated, often tortuous or sigmoid-shaped esophagus with significant retention of material. At this stage, symptoms often persist even if the LES has been disrupted by prior therapies, as the esophageal body itself has lost its functional capacity.[1, 4]

While HRM serves as the definitive gold standard for diagnosing the functional impairments defining achalasia [14, 1396], a comprehensive assessment of the condition, particularly its structural sequelae and the exclusion of alternative diagnoses, necessitates the integration of other modalities, such as TBE and EGD [1, 7].

Figure 2: High-Resolution Manometry of Achalasia subtypes[1, 5]

HRM is indispensable for characterizing the core physiological defects: impaired LES relaxation and abnormal esophageal peristalsis. Modern HRM systems utilize closely spaced pressure sensors along a catheter, providing detailed spatiotemporal pressure data across the entire esophagus, which is visualized as pressure topography plots [2, 4 sq.]. The key diagnostic metric is the Integrated Relaxation Pressure (IRP), which quantifies the adequacy of LES relaxation during swallowing; an elevated median IRP (above device-specific normal thresholds) signifies impaired relaxation [2, 7]. The pattern of esophageal body contractility (or lack thereof) further defines the achalasia subtypes according to the Chicago Classification v4.0 [2, 9]. Abbildung 2 from Savarino et al. [1, 5] illustrates these patterns: compared to the normal pattern showing a coordinated peristaltic wave following complete LES relaxation, Type 1 achalasia (classic) demonstrates failed peristalsis and absent pressurization; Type 2 achalasia (with compression) shows absent peristalsis accompanied by pan-esophageal pressurization in $\geq 20\%$ of swallows; and Type 3 achalasia (spastic) exhibits premature or spastic contractions in $\geq 20\%$ of swallows, often with high pressures, but no normal peristalsis [3, 167] [2, 11]. While HRM precisely defines functional disorder, it provides limited direct information about the resultant anatomical changes, such as dilation or tortuosity.

TBE complements HRM by providing a dynamic visualization of esophageal emptying and luminal morphology. During TBE, the patient swallows a barium suspension, and radiographs are typically taken at 1, 2, and 5 minutes [14, 1405] [1, 9]. In achalasia, TBE commonly reveals delayed emptying of barium from the esophagus, often quantified

Figure 3: Endoscopic and Timed Barium Esophagram findings in Achalasia[1, 9]

by a barium column height >2 cm at 5 minutes, as shown in Abbildung 3 [1, 9]. Morphologically, TBE can demonstrate esophageal dilation (varying from mild to severe) and characteristic tapering at the EGJ, known as the 'bird's beak' sign (Abbildung 3). In advanced, long-standing disease, significant dilation and tortuosity may lead to a 'sigmoid esophagus' appearance (Abbildung 3, right panel) [1, 9]. TBE is particularly valuable for assessing stasis and the degree of structural alteration, offering prognostic information and aiding treatment selection and follow-up [7, 197]. However, as a 2D projection technique, it lacks detailed information about the esophageal wall or precise cross-sectional geometry. EGD is primarily performed to exclude mechanical obstruction or malignancy (e.g., pseudoachalasia) that can mimic achalasia, which is a critical step before initiating achalasia-specific therapy [1, 7] [15, 1841]. While not diagnostic for the motility disorder itself, EGD may reveal findings suggestive of achalasia, including retained saliva or food residue in a dilated lumen and a characteristic resistance felt as the endoscope passes through a tight, often puckered LES (Abbildung 3, left panel) [1, 9]. Although EGD provides direct visualization of the mucosa, allowing for biopsy, it offers only localized 2D surface views, and estimations of diameter or length are subjective and highly dependent on factors such as insufflation levels [15, 1846]. Therefore, while each modality offers unique and essential diagnostic information, none alone provides a complete picture of both functional impairment and detailed 3D anatomical consequences in achalasia. The inherent limitations of these conventional 2D or functionally focused

assessments necessitate integrated computational approaches, such as 3D reconstruction, for a truly comprehensive understanding of patient-specific anatomy and physiology to guide modern, personalized management of achalasia.

2.2 Methodologies for 3D Esophageal Reconstruction and Validation

Generating accurate, patient-specific 3D models from clinical data is a core objective in computer-assisted diagnosis and therapy planning across various medical disciplines [16, 1] [17, 1]. Within gastroenterology, specifically for esophageal disorders such as achalasia, computational strategies have been investigated to overcome the limitations of conventional 2D or functional assessment [18, 898].

CT provides the most detailed non-invasive depiction of esophageal anatomy currently available owing to its inherent cross-sectional nature and high spatial resolution [18, 899]. The standard methodology involves segmenting the anatomical region on sequential axial images, followed by surface or volume rendering to create a 3D representation [17, 3]. This structure allows for detailed digital modeling of complex anatomical shapes [17, 1]. The resulting CT-derived mesh models offer high anatomical fidelity [17, 1], making CT the de facto ground truth standard for validating the structural accuracy of models derived from other data sources [19, 1], which is the role it serves in the present study. However, the associated ionizing radiation exposure, cost, and static nature of CT acquisition limit its routine use solely for achalasia management or frequent longitudinal monitoring [19, 1].

Consequently, considerable research has focused on extracting 3D information from more commonly employed diagnostic modalities, such as EGD [8, 865] [20, 1]. Standard computer vision techniques, including Structure-from-Motion (SfM), Shape-from-Shading (SfS), and Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), have been adapted for endoscopic video analysis [21, 1] [22, 346] [23, 1]. SfM attempts to reconstruct 3D structure and camera motion by tracking features across multiple video frames [21, 1]. SfS infers the shape from the way light interacts with the surface in a single image, assuming specific lighting and reflectance properties [22, 352]. SLAM techniques aim to build a map of the environment while simultaneously tracking the camera position within it [23, 2]. However, monocular vision-based approaches often struggle within the challenging intraluminal esophageal environment, which is characterized by poor lighting, specular highlights (difficult for SfS), tissue deformation (problematic for SfM/SLAM rigidity assumptions), variable illumination, and potential occlusions [24, 1090]. These challenges frequently result in reconstructions that are sparse or geometrically inaccurate [21, 1].

Recognizing the individual limitations of single modalities, multi-modal fusion strategies could represent a more promising approach. The specific *Esophagus Visualization* Software, whose validation is the subject of this study, exemplifies such an approach by building upon an initial prototype developed by Peter [9, 53 sq.] at the University of Augsburg. This system aims to generate a patient-specific 3D esophageal reconstruction by integrating anatomical information primarily from frontal TBE images with rich functional data provided by HRM, and optionally incorporating surface details derived from EGD images

[9, 53 sq.] [10, 8]. The core concept involves using the 2D TBE contour to define the overall geometry, calculating the shortest path, determining cross-sectional dimensions (width from TBE, shape refined by EGD if available), and appropriately stacking and tilting these cross-sections based on the center path to construct the 3D form [25, 13-15] [26, 19 sq.]. The temporally resolved pressure data from HRM is then mapped onto the surface of this generated 3D mesh and visualized using a clinically relevant color scale [25, 15]. This geometry-driven, multi-modal integration aims to produce anatomically plausible and clinically relevant 3D models [26, 17]. The validation of this specific reconstruction pipeline against the high-fidelity CT anatomical standard is the central focus of this study, employing quantitative geometric and volumetric metrics and adhering to data quality considerations [13, 13].

Given that this validation relies on advanced geometric comparison techniques, it is essential to establish a theoretical foundation for the underlying concepts and algorithms. A 3D model is a digital representation of an object’s geometry and topology in three-dimensional space, often used in medical applications for visualization, simulation, and quantitative assessment [27, 1]. In computational medical imaging, such 3D models are commonly represented in two primary forms: point clouds and meshes [27, 2]. A point cloud consists of a discrete set of data points in 3D space, each defined by coordinates (x, y, z), typically acquired from scanning technologies like laser scanners or photogrammetry, representing a sampled surface without explicit connectivity between points [28, 1]. In contrast, a mesh is a polygonal structure composed of vertices (points), edges (connections between vertices), and faces (typically triangles) that explicitly define the surface topology and geometry, enabling more structured analysis and manipulation [29, 10-12].

Building on these definitions, an explanation of the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm and Cloud-to-Mesh (C2M) distance metric should be outlined, which are pivotal for aligning and quantifying deviations between 3D models. The ICP algorithm, originally proposed by Besl and McKay [30, 239], is a widely adopted technique for rigid registration of point sets or meshes in 3D space. It iteratively minimizes the distance between a source point cloud (or mesh vertices) and a reference by alternating between correspondence estimation and transformation optimization [30, 239]. In each iteration, ICP identifies the closest points between the sets using a nearest-neighbour search, typically via a k-d tree for efficiency [31, 122]. A rigid transformation (rotation R and translation t) is then computed to minimize the mean squared error between matched pairs, often solved via singular value decomposition of the covariance matrix [30, 242]. Convergence is achieved when the root mean square distance change falls below a threshold, ensuring robust alignment even with initial misalignment, though it assumes sufficient overlap and can be sensitive to outliers [32, 2727]. Recent advancements have enhanced ICP’s robustness; for instance, Yang et al. [33, 1457] introduced a globally optimal ICP variant that incorporates branch-and-bound optimization to improve initialization and outlier handling in 3D registration tasks, achieving superior efficiency in applications such as remote sensing datasets. Similarly, De Magistris and Pajaziti [34, 12] proposed robust feature descriptors based on curvature and variance for ICP in noisy point clouds, reducing iterations by optimizing point matching in low-overlap scenarios.

Following alignment, Abbildung 4 shows how the C2M distance quantifies geometric

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of Cloud to Mesh (C2M) distance estimation method [35, 452]

congruence by computing the Distance from each Point in a point cloud to the nearest vertex on a reference mesh [35, 451]. This metric, implemented in tools like CloudCompare, employs spatial partitioning for efficient nearest-point queries [36]. For evaluation, C2M generates a scalar field of distances, enabling statistical analysis such as mean, standard deviation, and maximum deviation [36]. In this context, the Chamfer distance metric, which measures the average of the closest-point distances between two point clouds in both directions, is fundamental to C2M computations and provides a balanced measure of overall spatial deviation suitable for assessing point-to-surface congruence in 3D models [37, 3]. The Chamfer Distance (CD) between two point sets P_1 and P_2 can be formally defined as:

$$CD(P_1, P_2) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{|P_1|} \sum_{x \in P_1} \min_{y \in P_2} \|x - y\|^2 + \frac{1}{|P_2|} \sum_{y \in P_2} \min_{x \in P_1} \|y - x\|^2 \right)$$

where P_1 refers to the compared point cloud and P_2 to the reference point cloud [38, 6]. This averaging approach of the chamfer distance is particularly effective for quantifying typical discrepancies and global similarity [37, 3]. However, it may smooth out extreme outliers compared to maximization metrics, such as the Hausdorff distance [37, 3]. Recent studies, such as those evaluating mesh quality in anatomical modeling, emphasize Chamfer distance for its robustness in balancing noise across datasets, facilitating reliable statistical summaries of average model fidelity [38, 15 sq.]. For 3D model comparison, Chamfer distance thus enables focused analysis of aggregated volumetric and morphological accuracy in applications like organ reconstruction [38, 1]. These methods collectively enable precise validation, with ICP ensuring alignment and C2M providing quantifiable metrics grounded in distance transforms for reliable shape analysis.

3 Procedure

This section delineates the complete methodological framework employed for the validation of the multi-modal esophageal 3D reconstruction software. The plan for data acquisition is outlined along with the traits of the patient cohort. It then details the meticulous process for generating the anatomical ground truth models from CT data, the specific reconstruction and refinement pipeline for the software models under review, and the rigorous quantitative criteria used for the final comparative analysis

3.1 Data Acquisition and Cohort Description

The primary objective of this study necessitated the collection of patient datasets encompassing both the input modalities potentially utilized by the reconstruction software (primarily TBE, EGD, and HRM) and the corresponding high-resolution CT scans to serve as the anatomical ground truth reference. Recognizing the challenges in obtaining fully comprehensive multi-modal datasets complete with concurrent CT imaging for a rare condition such as achalasia, a pragmatic approach combining clinically acquired data and publicly available resources was adopted for this initial validation phase. Ethical considerations were paramount; all data utilized were fully anonymized prior to analysis, adhering to the institutional guidelines for data privacy and research ethics.

The validation cohort comprised a total of six distinct patient cases selected to represent a relevant, albeit limited, range of clinical presentations and demographics. The patients' ages ranged from 15 to 60 years, including both male and female individuals, reflecting the broad spectrum affected by esophageal motility disorders. This heterogeneity was advantageous for assessing the robustness of the model across different anatomical variations.

A cornerstone case (Patient 1) was sourced through direct clinical collaboration with the Department of Gastroenterology at the University Hospital Augsburg (UKA), facilitated by Dr. Sandra Nagl. While this patient presented with an esophageal tumor, a pathology distinct from achalasia, an expert review deemed the case highly relevant. The associated esophageal morphology was considered analogous to advanced achalasia phenotypes, making it a suitable and complex test for the software's geometric fidelity. Critically, this UKA case provided a uniquely rich dataset encompassing all potential input modalities for the software (TBE, EGD, and HRM) alongside the requisite reference standard CT scan. This allowed for a comprehensive assessment scenario in which the software performance could be evaluated against the ground truth using all available input modalities.

To augment this single, intensely documented clinical case and specifically include confirmed achalasia presentations, data from five additional patients (Patients 2-6) were retrospectively collected from publicly accessible medical imaging archives, more specifically Radiopaedia.org [12]. These cases were selected based on the availability of both TBE images, suitable as input for the *Esophagus Visualization* reconstruction algorithm, and corresponding diagnostic CT scans of the thorax/abdomen, which allowed for the generation of ground truth 3D esophageal models. While these public repository cases provided confirmed achalasia diagnoses and the essential pairing of TBE with CT

for validation, they typically lacked the accompanying HRM or detailed endoscopic video recordings available for the UKA case. This limitation restricted the evaluation of the software’s full multimodal integration capability for these five specific cases but critically allowed for the core validation objective: comparing TBE-driven software reconstructions against CT-derived anatomical reality across multiple achalasia patients.

3.2 Constructing the Groundtruth: 3D Reconstruction of the Esophagus from CT Data

The establishment of a robust and anatomically accurate ground truth standard is fundamental to any rigorous validation study of medical image reconstruction algorithms. For this investigation, 3D models derived from high-resolution CT scans were designated as the reference standard owing to CT’s inherent capability of CT to depict detailed cross-sectional anatomy. The generation of these ground truth models was a meticulous process, critically dependent on both expert anatomical knowledge and specialized medical imaging software.

Figure 5: Workflow for generating the CT-based ground truth model

The procedural framework for establishing the anatomical ground truth is illustrated in Abbildung 5. The foundational step involved precise delineation of the esophagus within each patient’s CT dataset. This crucial segmentation process was performed collaboratively with our clinical domain expert, Dr. Sandra Nagl from the Department of Gastroenterology at the UKA. Leveraging her extensive clinical experience with esophageal anatomy and achalasia pathology, Dr. Nagl meticulously analyzed each axial slice of the CT scans for all six patients. The entire longitudinal extent of the esophagus, from its proximal origin to the gastroesophageal junction, was carefully identified and its boundaries were delineated on the axial images. This expert-driven, slice-by-slice segmentation ensured that the resulting contours accurately reflected the

true anatomical extent and configuration of the esophagus, accounting for variations in shape, dilation, and position relative to surrounding mediastinal structures. These expert-defined contours formed the essential two-dimensional input for the subsequent 3D model generation.

The conversion of these stacked, 2D segmentations into coherent 3D surface models was accomplished using the open-source medical image computing platform 3D Slicer[39]. As illustrated in the 'Construct 3D Model' step in Abbildung 5, this process transformed the 2D delineations into a topologically coherent, 3D polygonal surface model. Initially, the complete axial CT DICOM series for each patient was imported into the Slicer environment.

Within Slicer's 'Segment Editor' module, the expert-derived contours were loaded as a label map, allowing for verification and minor adjustments to ensure slice-to-slice consistency. The core 3D model generation was then performed using Slicer's integrated modeling capabilities, which computationally process the stacked 2D contours and apply surface generation algorithms to interpolate between slices. Finally, upon satisfactory generation and refinement, the 3D model for each patient's esophagus was exported from Slicer in a standard mesh file format (e.g., STL), suitable for subsequent computational analysis and direct comparison with the models generated by the *EsophagusVisualization* software. This rigorous process, combining expert anatomical delineation with the computational tools of 3D Slicer, yielded six patient-specific, high-fidelity 3D esophageal models that served as the definitive anatomical ground truth for this validation study.

3.3 Multi-Modal Software Model for 3D Reconstruction using EsophagusVisualization

The generation of 3D esophageal models from clinical data, beyond the direct segmentation of volumetric CT scans, requires sophisticated computational approaches capable of integrating information from diverse, often lower-dimensional, sources. This section details the specific methodology employed by the *EsophagusVisualization* software to reconstruct the esophagus using multi-modal inputs, primarily TBE and HRM, with optional integration of EGD data. Furthermore, the essential post-processing steps undertaken to refine the software's output into anatomically plausible and computationally robust 3D meshes suitable for rigorous validation is detailed.

3.3.1 Generation of 3D Esophageal Models with EsophagusVisualization

The reconstruction pipeline within the *EsophagusVisualization* software begins with the loading and processing of patient-specific diagnostic data, encompassing TBE, EGD, and HRM inputs. Abbildung 6 provides a schematic overview of this comprehensive workflow. Foundational to this process is the TBE, typically a single frontal X-ray image capturing the barium-filled esophageal lumen. Prior to import, the relevant esophageal contours on the TBE image must be meticulously delineated to define the 2D projection of the esophageal shape. This initial segmentation was performed for this study under the guidance of our clinical expert (Dr. Nagl) to ensure anatomical accuracy. Similarly, if

EGD data is incorporated, representative cross-sectional images require pre-identification and segmentation of the lumen while being processed in the software. Complementing this structural data, the temporal pressure recordings from HRM are imported, typically in a processed CSV format derived from the clinical manometry system. For the patient cases acquired from Radiopaedia.org, this HRM data was not available. This omission, however, does not compromise the core geometric validation of this study, as the software utilizes HRM data exclusively for mapping pressure values onto the model’s surface for visualization; it does not influence the underlying calculation of the 3D model’s geometry, which is the primary focus of this accuracy assessment.

Figure 6: Workflow for generating the 3D Esophageal Reconstruction

Once the input data is loaded, the user interacts with the software to provide critical anatomical landmarks and reference points necessary for the reconstruction algorithm. This involves annotating the TBE image within the software’s interface to precisely define: (i) the segmentation of the whole esophagus according to the TBE image; (ii) the precise locations corresponding to at least two distinct HRM sensor positions along the esophageal length; (iii) the location of the EGJ, serving as the distal anchor point; (iv) the location of the upper boundary of the LES; and optionally (v) the location of the zero position and segmentation of the EGD images, if they were provided. These user-defined points, alongside the pre-segmented TBE and EGD contour, provide the spatial framework for the subsequent 3D model construction.

The core algorithm within the *Esophagus Visualization*, significantly enhanced from the initial prototype described by Peter [9, 13] to address limitations in handling non-linear esophageal morphologies, proceeds as follows: First, it computes the shortest path within

the 2D esophageal contour on the TBE image, connecting the identified EGJ point to the defined upper esophageal boundary. This shortest path serves as an approximation of the HRM catheter’s trajectory and the esophageal centerline in the frontal plane. Subsequently, to establish a more anatomically representative centerline, especially in cases of dilation or tortuosity, a ‘center path’ is calculated. This involves determining the esophageal width along lines perpendicular to the shortest path at numerous points. The perpendicular orientation at each point is estimated using linear regression on local segments of the shortest path, and the width is measured by finding the intersections of this perpendicular line with the esophageal contours. The midpoints of these width lines define the center path.

The 3D shape is then constructed by computationally stacking cross-sections along this calculated center path, as depicted in the ‘Construct 3D Model’ phase of Abbildung 6. In the absence of EGD data, the software assumes a circular cross-section at each point along the center path, with the diameter derived directly from the calculated esophageal width on the TBE image at that corresponding perpendicular. If EGD images are provided and annotated (linking specific endoscopic views to corresponding heights along the esophagus), the software refines the cross-sectional shape. Instead of assuming a perfect circle, it uses the actual luminal contour segmented from the relevant EGD image (or interpolates between available EGD contours) to define the shape of the cross-section at that specific height. To account for the esophagus’s curvature and tilt in 3D space, each stacked cross-section is rotated appropriately. The angle of rotation for each cross-section is determined by the local slope of the center path at that point, calculated from the linear regression analysis used previously to find the perpendicular width. Finally, the temporal HRM pressure data is mapped onto the surface of the generated 3D mesh. Using the annotated HRM sensor positions on the TBE image and the known inter-sensor spacing, the software interpolates the pressure reading along the esophageal length (represented by the center path) for each time point in the manometry recording. These pressure values are then visualized using a pre-defined color scale applied directly to the corresponding locations on the 3D mesh surface, allowing for dynamic visualization of pressure changes over the swallowing cycle. The resulting output within *Esophagus Visualization* is an interactive 3D model representing the reconstructed esophageal geometry with superimposed, temporally varying pressure data.

3.3.2 Post-Processing and Mesh Refinement using Blender

While *Esophagus Visualization* generates a comprehensive 3D representation integrating multi-modal data, following the workflow outlined in Abbildung 6, the process of exporting this internal model to a standard mesh format (e.g., STL for 3D printing or further analysis) revealed certain limitations inherent in the reconstruction and mesh generation algorithms as currently implemented. As conceptually discussed by Schneider [26, 18] regarding the challenges of creating well-formed meshes from discrete data points or cross-sections, the exported meshes from *Esophagus Visualization* often exhibited artifacts and topological inconsistencies requiring external post-processing. These issues stemmed primarily from the methodology of stacking and tilting discrete 2D cross-sections (whether

circles or EGD-derived polygons) to form the 3D structure. Abrupt changes in diameter or sharp alterations in the calculated path slope between adjacent points could lead to self-intersections between consecutive cross-sectional planes, overlapping faces, or non-manifold geometry where edges were shared by more than two faces. Furthermore, the interpolation between defined cross-sections, especially when transitioning between circular approximations and potentially complex EGD-derived polygons, could sometimes generate unrealistic surface topology or localized defects. These artifacts, while potentially minor in the interactive viewer, become problematic when requiring a clean, watertight, manifold mesh for quantitative volumetric and geometric analysis, or physical 3D printing.

Figure 7: Post-Processing Workflow in Blender

To address these limitations and produce high-quality meshes suitable for validation against the CT ground truth, a dedicated post-processing Step following the workflow outlined in Abbildung 6, was established using the open-source 3D modeling software, Blender [40]. Each mesh exported from *EsophagusVisualization* was imported into Blender for detailed inspection and refinement. The primary task involved identifying and correcting the aforementioned topological errors as seen in Abbildung 7. Problematic regions exhibiting self-intersections or unrealistic geometry (e.g., sharp ridges or concavities resulting from interpolation artifacts) were manually selected and excised using Blender’s mesh editing tools. Subsequently, the resulting gaps were meticulously filled by generating new, appropriately smoothed mesh geometry. This typically involved using techniques such as bridging edge loops between the boundaries of the excised region or employing sculpting tools to create a more anatomically plausible surface transition, ensuring continuity with the surrounding unaffected mesh areas. The objective was to manually curate the mesh, guided by anatomical knowledge, to eliminate computational artifacts while preserving the overall shape and dimensions dictated by the reconstruction

algorithm.

Following this manual refinement phase, an automated cleaning step was performed utilizing Blender’s integrated ‘3D Print Toolbox’ add-on. This specialized toolset includes functions designed to analyze and repair mesh geometry specifically for 3D printing, which inherently requires clean, manifold, and watertight models. The ‘Clean Up’ functions within the toolbox were employed to automatically detect and attempt repair of residual errors, such as non-manifold edges (edges connected to more than two faces), zero-area faces, thin faces, self-intersections that might have been missed during manual inspection, and small holes. The ‘Make Manifold’ operation was used to ensure the final mesh represented a completely enclosed volume without gaps. This combined approach of targeted manual correction of gross artifacts followed by automated cleaning of finer geometric inconsistencies proved effective in transforming the initially exported, sometimes flawed, meshes into topologically sound, manifold, and visually realistic 3D representations of the achalasia esophagus.

3.4 Validation Methodology: Comparing Software Models to CT Ground Truth

Following the generation of 3D esophageal models using both the reference CT data (via Slicer and expert segmentation) and the *Esophagus Visualization* software (integrating multi-modal inputs and refined in Blender), a rigorous methodology was required to quantitatively and qualitatively compare these representations. This validation phase is crucial to ascertain the software model’s fidelity in capturing patient-specific esophageal anatomy. The process involved careful pre-processing to ensure comparability, followed by standardized geometric and volumetric comparisons using specialized software tools.

3.4.1 Pre-Processing for Comparative Analysis: Height Standardization and Anatomical Segmentation

A fundamental prerequisite for any meaningful geometric or volumetric comparison between two 3D models is ensuring they exist within a common and correctly scaled spatial reference frame. Abbildung 6 illustrates the systematic four-step approach employed for the complete validation methodology. While both the CT-derived ground truth and the software-generated models represent the same patient’s esophagus, inherent differences in acquisition parameters, coordinate systems, and reconstruction scaling factors necessitate explicit standardization, particularly concerning the height. The initial step involved precisely determining the vertical extent of the esophagus as represented in both the CT-derived model and the corresponding *Esophagus Visualization* software model, as depicted in the ‘Pre-process 3D model’ phase of Abbildung 8. For the software-generated models, this was achieved interactively within the *Esophagus Visualization* interface, which is built upon Plotly graphing libraries. The reconstructed esophageal height was measured by calculating the difference between the Z-coordinates of the most proximal and distal points of the 3D mesh. A similar process was applied to the CT-derived models, typically by loading them into Blender and measuring the maximum

dimension along the principal longitudinal axis, ensuring consistent anatomical landmarks were used for both model types.

Figure 8: Validation Workflow for the 3D Esophageal Reconstruction

With the true height established for each corresponding pair of models, the next critical step was scaling them to ensure identical heights before comparison. Both the CT-derived ground truth mesh and the corresponding post-processed *Esophagus Visualization* mesh were imported into the Blender environment. Using Blender’s precise scaling transformations, the dimension of each model along its primary longitudinal axis (typically aligned with the Z-axis in Blender) was uniformly scaled to match the pre-determined height measurement extracted in the previous step.

3.4.2 Quantitative Geometric Comparison using CloudCompare

To objectively quantify the geometric congruence between the software-generated esophageal models and the CT-derived ground truth, a quantitative comparison was performed as outlined in the ‘Geometric Comparison’ phase of the validation framework (Abbildung 8). The methodology employed is conceptually analogous to established workflows for visualizing pairwise morphological variation in 3D models, such as the approach detailed by White and Campione [41, 16]. The entire process was executed using the open-source point cloud and mesh analysis software, CloudCompare (v2.12) [36], and comprised two primary stages: rigid registration of the models followed by distance computation.

Abbildung 9 provides a comprehensive visual summary of this entire quantitative comparison workflow. As illustrated in the second panel of Abbildung 9, these models

were defined with three key anatomical regions for sub-analysis: the proximal upper tubular esophagus, the lower tubular esophagus, and the distal 'LES Region', which is operationally defined in this paper as a combined segment that includes the sphincter and the adjoining lower tubular portion. This division is clinically pertinent as achalasia pathophysiology and therapeutic interventions often have differential effects on these distinct zones. Based on clinical relevance, where the distal sphincter and the immediately proximal region are critical for diagnosis and treatment efficacy (often manifesting the characteristic 'bird's beak' narrowing), the 'LES Region' segment was operationally defined as the distal-most 10 cm of the esophagus. This resulted in six distinct mesh objects for each patient: CT-Upper Tubular, CT-Lower Tubular, CT-'LES Region', Software-Upper Tubular, Software-Lower Tubular and Software-'LES Region'.

Figure 9: Screenshots of the Validation Workflow for the 3D Esophageal Reconstruction

Using these separated 3D Models, alignment, was crucial for ensuring that both models existed within a common spatial coordinate system. Due to potential significant initial differences in orientation and position, a manual pre-alignment step was first performed interactively within CloudCompare to achieve coarse spatial correspondence between the software-derived mesh (the 'model') and the CT-derived mesh (the 'reference'). Following manual pre-alignment, the fine alignment was performed using the ICP algorithm. The ICP algorithm iteratively refines the alignment by: (1) finding the closest point on the reference surface for each point (or a sample of points) on the model to be aligned, (2) calculating the rigid transformation (rotation and translation) that minimizes the sum of squared distances between these corresponding point pairs, and (3) applying this transformation to the model to be aligned. The ICP process was configured to iteratively refine the alignment until the root-mean-square (RMS) difference between iterations fell below a stringent threshold of 0.000010. To ensure computational efficiency while maintaining sufficient surface representation, a random sampling limit of 50,000 points

was utilized during the registration.

Once the software-derived mesh was precisely aligned with the CT ground truth, the geometric deviation between the two surfaces was quantified using CloudCompare's C2M distance computation tool. This algorithm calculates the distance similar to the Chamfer Distance from each vertex in the aligned software model to the surface of the CT reference model. For this analysis, the 'signed distances' option was deactivated, meaning the resulting scalar field represents the absolute magnitude of the spatial deviation at each point on the surface. The C2M distance computation generates a scalar field that is mapped as a color gradient onto the surface of the SW-Model, as shown in the final panel of Abbildung 9. This color map provides an intuitive, qualitative visualization of the error distribution across the esophageal surface, complementing the quantitative statistical analysis. This entire procedure was performed for the esophagus as a whole, as well as for each of the three pre-defined anatomical subregions to enable a more granular assessment of the software's geometric fidelity.

3.4.3 Comparative Volumetric Analysis

Beyond geometric surface congruence, assessing the accuracy of volumetric representation is critical, particularly given the clinical significance of esophageal dilation in achalasia and the potential for treatments like POEM to induce volumetric remodeling. The validation methodology included a direct comparison of the volumes calculated for the software-derived models and the CT-derived ground truth models, as outlined in the 'Quantify volumetric differences' phase of Abbildung 8.

The calculation of volumes for the models generated by the *Esophagus Visualization* software was integrated within the software itself, forming part of its automated metric output pipeline, as conceptually described in the reports by Peter and Krafft [9, 14] [25, 16]. The underlying principle involved computationally summing the volumes of the thin, stacked cylindrical or polygon-based cross-sections used to construct the 3D model. The volume of each 'slice' was determined by multiplying its calculated cross-sectional area by its effective height (derived from the distance along the calculated center path). Subsequently the total volume was obtained by summing these incremental slice volumes along the entire length of the reconstructed segment. This integrated calculation provided a direct volumetric readout from the software's internal geometric representation.

For the CT-derived ground truth models volume calculation required an external tool capable of handling standard mesh formats (e.g., STL). For this purpose, the Blender software environment, specifically utilizing the integrated '3D Print Toolbox' add-on, was employed. This add-on includes functionality to accurately compute the volume of watertight 3D meshes, a necessary feature for preparing models for 3D printing but equally applicable for quantitative analysis.

Finally, the volumes obtained from the *Esophagus Visualization* software were directly compared against the corresponding volumes calculated using the Blender 3D Print. This comparison allowed for the quantification of volumetric accuracy, revealing any systematic tendencies of the software model to overestimate or underestimate esophageal volume relative to the CT reference standard, providing another critical dimension to

the overall validation assessment.

4 Results

This section presents the quantitative and qualitative findings from the comparative validation of the *Esophagus Visualization* software’s 3D reconstructions against CT-derived ground truth models. The results are presented separately for the index case with complete multi-modal input (Patient 1) and the subsequent cohort where reconstructions relied primarily on TBE data (Patients 2-6). The analysis encompasses geometric and volumetric comparisons, an internal validation of the software’s volume calculation algorithm, and an investigation into the regional distribution of reconstruction error. For a comprehensive overview, specific values cited in the following subsections that are not depicted in the figures can be viewed in the supplementary datasheet available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17967799>).

4.1 Patient 1 from the University Hospital Augsburg: Complete Input Data Coverage for 3D-Reconstruction

Patient 1’s dataset, sourced from the University Hospital Augsburg, provided a unique opportunity to evaluate the software’s performance when utilizing the full complement of potential input data: TBE, EGD, and HRM, alongside the reference CT scan. Three distinct 3D reconstructions were generated, corresponding to the TBE images acquired at 1, 2, and 5 minutes post-barium ingestion, with EGD cross-sectional data incorporated into each.

4.1.1 Geometric Comparison

The analysis revealed that the geometric fidelity of the reconstructions from Patient 1 varied significantly depending on the TBE acquisition time point used as the primary input. When considering the whole esophagus, the reconstruction derived from the 2-minute TBE image yielded the highest overall accuracy. It registered a mean C2M distance of 0.293 cm with a standard deviation of 0.236 cm. This optimal result is visually contextualized within the entire patient cohort in *Abbildung 11*. In comparison, the models generated from the 1-minute and 5-minute TBE images produced larger geometric deviations, with mean C2M distances recorded at 0.373 cm (SD 0.268 cm) and 0.348 cm (SD 0.301 cm), respectively. The mean deviation of the optimal 2-minute model was therefore approximately 22% lower than that of the 1-minute model, representing a substantial improvement in geometric correspondence. A more granular analysis was performed on the anatomically segmented regions of the esophagus to assess the consistency of these findings across different zones. For the upper tubular esophagus, the performance differences between the time points were even more pronounced. The reconstructions based on the 1-minute and 5-minute TBES resulted in mean C2M distances of 0.384 cm and 0.394 cm, respectively. The model based on the 2-minute TBE, however,

Figure 10: Patient 1 3D-Model comparison derived from the 2-minute TBE image in CloudCompare

demonstrated a substantially lower mean deviation of just 0.177 cm (SD 0.152 cm). This result, also highlighted in Abbildung 11, was less than half the deviation observed in the other two models for this segment, indicating a particularly high level of accuracy in reconstructing the more uniform tubular anatomy when using the optimal TBE data.

This performance trend was maintained in the analysis of the clinically pertinent 'LES Region'. Here, the 1-minute and 5-minute reconstructions yielded mean C2M distances of 0.379 cm and 0.305 cm, respectively. The optimal 2-minute model again produced the lowest geometric error, with a mean C2M distance of 0.259 cm (SD 0.207 cm). The consistent superiority of the 2-minute TBE reconstruction across the entire esophagus and its distinct anatomical subregions is a clear and quantifiable finding of this analysis. These quantitative results were strongly corroborated by qualitative visual assessments of the superimposed 3D models. As exemplified in the CloudCompare visualization for Patient 1 in Abbildung 10, the software-generated model exhibits a high degree of morphological correspondence to the CT-derived ground truth. The color-mapped deviation analysis rendered on the model's surface, which displays error from blue (low) to red (high), shows a predominantly green and blue surface, indicating that the majority of the model's vertices lie in close proximity to the reference surface. Patches of yellow, representing moderate deviation, are primarily localized to areas of high curvature or abrupt changes in diameter. Key anatomical structures, most notably the characteristic tapering of the distal esophagus and the overall configuration of the 'LES Region', were observed to be faithfully reproduced by the software model.

Figure 11: All Patients C2M Distance from CloudCompare at optimal time points

4.1.2 Volumetric Comparison

A comparative volumetric analysis was conducted between the optimal software-generated model for Patient 1 and the corresponding CT-derived ground truth. The analysis showed a small discrepancy between the two measurements. The absolute difference in the calculated volumes of the two models was 9.63 cm^3 . This numerical result is visually represented in the correlation plot in Abbildung 13, which compares the software-calculated volumes against the CT ground truth volumes for all patients in the cohort. The data point representing Patient 1 is located in the upper-right quadrant of the plot, positioned in very close proximity to the diagonal line that indicates perfect agreement. This position on the plot is consistent with the small numerical difference recorded between the software model's volume and the CT reference volume. The low volumetric difference observed for Patient 1 aligns with the low geometric C2M distances reported for this patient in the preceding section.

4.2 Patients 2-6 from Open-Source Data: Limited Input Data Coverage for 3D-Reconstruction

The evaluation was extended to Patients 2 through 6, whose datasets comprised TBE images and HRM data, but lacked corresponding EGD inputs. This allowed for assessment of the software's core reconstruction capability based primarily on TBE geometry, representing a more common clinical data availability scenario. For each patient, reconstructions were generated based on the available TBE time points (1, 2, and 5

minutes).

Figure 12: Patient 2 3D-Model comparison derived from the 5-minute TBE image in CloudCompare

4.2.1 Geometric Comparison

The analysis revealed greater inter-patient and intra-patient variability in geometric accuracy compared to the multi-modal reconstruction of Patient 1. While the optimal TBE acquisition time point for achieving the highest fidelity varied among individuals, a general trend was observed where reconstructions based on later TBE acquisitions, particularly the 5-minute image, frequently yielded the lowest C2M distances.

When analyzing the whole esophagus, the optimal mean C2M distances for this cohort ranged from a minimum of 0.301 cm to a maximum of 0.544 cm, as visualized in Abbildung 11. For Patient 2, the optimal reconstruction was derived from the 5-minute TBE, resulting in a mean C2M distance of 0.329 cm (SD 0.351 cm). Patient 3 presented an exception to the general trend, with the 2-minute TBE providing the most accurate model at 0.352 cm (SD 0.276 cm). For Patient 4, the 5-minute TBE again proved optimal, yielding the lowest mean C2M distance of the entire TBE-only cohort at 0.301 cm (SD 0.255 cm). Conversely, Patient 5 exhibited the largest geometric deviation, with the best-performing model (from the 5-minute TBE) registering a mean C2M distance of 0.544 cm (SD 0.403 cm), a value that exceeds the 0.5 cm clinical acceptability threshold. Finally, Patient 6 followed the predominant pattern, with the 5-minute TBE reconstruction providing the lowest error at a mean C2M distance of 0.320 cm (SD 0.316 cm).

A more detailed segmental analysis was performed to investigate geometric fidelity within the distinct anatomical regions of the esophagus. In the upper tubular esophagus,

the results showed variability in which time point produced the most accurate reconstruction. For Patient 2, the 5-minute TBE model was optimal, with a mean C2M of 0.351 cm (SD 0.339 cm). For Patient 3, the 1-minute TBE model yielded the lowest deviation for this segment at 0.213 cm (SD 0.211 cm), differing from the optimal time point for its whole esophagus. Patient 4's most accurate tubular reconstruction came from the 5-minute TBE, with a mean C2M of 0.255 cm (SD 0.229 cm). Similarly, the 5-minute TBE was optimal for Patient 5, with a mean C2M of 0.377 cm (SD 0.231 cm), and for Patient 6, which had the lowest tubular deviation in this cohort at 0.175 cm (SD 0.165 cm).

The analysis of the 'LES Region' revealed the most significant variability in geometric accuracy across the cohort, a finding that is also represented in *Abbildung 11*. For Patient 2, the 1-minute TBE produced a reconstruction with a mean C2M distance of only 0.149 cm (SD 0.148 cm), which was the lowest recorded deviation for any segment across the entire TBE-only cohort. For Patient 3, the optimal time point for this region was the 2-minute TBE, resulting in a mean C2M of 0.256 cm (SD 0.256 cm). For the remaining patients, the 5-minute TBE consistently provided the most accurate model of the distal esophagus. Patient 4's optimal model had a mean C2M of 0.371 cm (SD 0.276 cm). Patient 5 showed the highest deviation in this segment as well, with a mean C2M of 0.491 cm (SD 0.341 cm) for its best model. Lastly, Patient 6's optimal reconstruction for the 'LES Region' had a mean C2M of 0.316 cm (SD 0.317 cm).

Qualitative visual inspection of the superimposed 3D models and their corresponding color-mapped deviation plots provided further insight into these quantitative findings. In general, the software-generated models for Patients 2-6 showed good overall morphological agreement with their CT counterparts. However, the magnitude and extent of local geometric deviations were visibly more pronounced than in the multi-modal reconstruction for Patient 1. *Abbildung 12* provides a representative visualization of this for Patient 2, who exhibited the largest mean C2M distance. The color map on the software model, which displays error from blue (low) to red (high), shows widespread areas of both green and yellow, indicating significant regions of geometric discrepancy distributed across the surface. This contrasts sharply with the visual results for Patient 1, shown in *Abbildung 10*, where the surface is predominantly blue, and areas of moderate deviation are smaller and more localized. The visual evidence from figures like *Abbildung 12* confirms that while the overall shape is captured, the TBE-only reconstructions for Patients 2-6 contain more frequent and larger surface deviations from the ground truth anatomy compared to the EGD-informed reconstruction.

4.2.2 Volumetric Comparison

The comparative volumetric analysis for Patients 2-6 reinforced the geometric findings and highlighted the impact of relying solely on TBE for reconstruction. Consistent with the geometric results, the smallest absolute volume differences between the software models and the CT ground truth were most often observed for reconstructions based on the latest TBE time point (TBE 3).

For Patient 2, the optimal reconstruction from the 5-minute TBE yielded a software-

Figure 13: Esophageal volume comparison: *Esophagus Visualization* vs. CT ground truth

calculated volume of 88.86 cm^3 , compared to a CT ground truth volume of 65.26 cm^3 . This represents an absolute volume difference of 31.19 cm^3 , with the software model's volume being larger than the reference. Patient 3 showed the smallest volumetric discrepancy in this cohort. The 5-minute TBE reconstruction resulted in a software model volume of 99.47 cm^3 , which was very close to the CT ground truth volume of 102.34 cm^3 , producing an absolute difference of only 2.87 cm^3 . In this case, the software model's volume was slightly smaller than the reference. For Patient 4, the optimal 5-minute TBE reconstruction produced a software volume of 57.05 cm^3 against a CT volume of 71.35 cm^3 , resulting in an absolute difference of 14.30 cm^3 . The software volume was again smaller than the CT reference. Patient 5 exhibited the second-largest volumetric difference; the 5-minute TBE model had a volume of 46.88 cm^3 , whereas the CT ground truth volume was 18.22 cm^3 , leading to an absolute difference of 30.83 cm^3 . Similar to Patient 2, the software model's volume was substantially larger than the reference. Finally, for Patient 6, the 5-minute TBE reconstruction yielded a software volume of 38.64 cm^3 compared to a CT volume of 49.33 cm^3 , resulting in an absolute difference of 10.59 cm^3 . Thus the software model's volume was smaller than the CT reference. In summary, for the optimal time point, the software models produced larger volumes than the CT ground truth for two patients (2 and 5) and smaller volumes for three patients (3, 4, and 6).

These findings are visually summarized in the correlation plot presented in Abbildung 13.

This plot displays the relationship between the software-calculated volume and the CT ground truth volume for the optimal reconstruction of each patient in the study. The data points for the entire cohort show a strong positive correlation, confirmed by a calculated R^2 value of 0.772 ($p < 0.05$, indicating statistical significance). The individual data points for Patients 2 through 6 are scattered around the diagonal line of perfect agreement. The points for Patient 3, Patient 4, and Patient 6 lie relatively close to this line, visually representing their smaller volumetric differences.

4.3 Validating the In-house 3D-Reconstruction: Volume Calculation

Additionally a critical internal validation was conducted to verify the accuracy of the volume computation algorithm implemented within the *EsophagusVisualization* software. This analysis was distinct from the comparison against the external CT ground truth; its purpose was to determine if the software’s reported volume accurately reflected the true geometric volume of the 3D model it generated. To achieve this, the volumetric measurements reported directly by the *EsophagusVisualization* software were compared to volumes calculated independently on the identical, exported software-generated meshes. This comparative analysis was performed on the complete set of 18 3D models generated throughout the study, covering the full range of patients and reconstruction parameters.

Figure 14: *EsophagusVisualization* volume accuracy vs. external Blender validation

The results of this internal validation demonstrated an extremely high degree of

concordance between the software’s internal calculation and the external Blender-based measurement. The relationship between the two sets of measurements is visually presented in the scatter plot in Abbildung 14. This plot compares the *Esophagus Visualization* Volume (x-axis) against the Blender Reference Volume (y-axis) for all 18 models. The data points form a tight, linear cluster that aligns almost perfectly along the diagonal line of perfect agreement, indicating a one-to-one relationship. The strength of this linear correlation is quantitatively confirmed by the coefficient of determination, which was calculated to be $R^2 = 0.9925$ ($p < 0.001$, indicating high statistical significance).

A numerical analysis of the differences between the two measurement methods further supports this finding. Across all 18 models, which ranged in volume from approximately 36 cm^3 to over 147 cm^3 , the absolute differences between the software’s reported volume and the Blender reference volume were consistently small. The mean absolute difference between the two methods was calculated to be 3.24 cm^3 , with a corresponding mean percentage error of approximately 3.5%. These small, negligible discrepancies fall well within the expected range of computational precision differences that can arise between distinct software implementations and algorithms. The outcome of this internal validation confirms that the volume calculation method implemented within the *Esophagus Visualization* software accurately and reliably reports the geometric volume of the 3D models it generates. Therefore, any volumetric discrepancies observed in the preceding comparisons against the CT ground truth models can be confidently attributed to actual differences in the reconstructed shapes themselves, rather than to any inaccuracy in the software’s internal volume reporting mechanism.

4.4 Regional Variation in Geometric Accuracy

To further investigate the distribution of geometric error along the cranio-caudal axis of the esophagus, a dedicated sub-analysis was performed. This analysis involved a more granular segmentation of the distal esophagus, separating the previously combined ‘Lower Tubular + Sphincter’ region into two distinct segments: the ‘Lower Tubular’ esophagus and the ‘LES Region’ as shown under Unterunterabschnitt 3.4.2 in Abbildung 9. The mean C2M distances were then calculated and aggregated for the TBE-only patient cohort (Patients 2-6) across these three anatomically defined regions: the ‘Upper Tubular’ esophagus, the ‘Lower Tubular’ esophagus, and the whole ‘LES Region’. The objective of this analysis was to determine whether a spatial pattern existed in the reconstruction error.

The results of this sub-analysis, presented in Abbildung 15, reveal a non-uniform distribution of geometric error across the three esophageal segments. The mean C2M distance was found to be lowest in the most proximal segment and comparatively higher in the two more distal segments. The ‘Upper Tubular’ region, represented by the leftmost bar in Abbildung 15, registered the lowest mean geometric deviation, with a C2M distance of approximately 0.27 cm. This value indicates the highest level of geometric accuracy among the three analyzed regions.

In contrast, the analysis of the ‘Lower Tubular’ region showed a markedly higher mean C2M distance. As depicted by the middle bar in Abbildung 15, the mean geometric error

Figure 15: Gravity analysis of Esophagus Regions

in this segment was approximately 0.325 cm. This represents a substantial increase in deviation compared to the upper segment. Similarly, the 'LES Region', the most distal segment, also demonstrated an elevated level of reconstruction error. The rightmost bar in Abbildung 15 shows a mean C2M distance of approximately 0.32 cm, a value nearly as high as that recorded for the 'Lower Tubular' region and significantly greater than the error in the 'Upper Tubular' segment.

A direct comparison of these values quantifies the observed regional differences in reconstruction accuracy. The mean geometric error in the 'Lower Tubular' region was approximately 20.4% greater than that recorded in the 'Upper Tubular' region. The error in the 'LES Region' was similarly higher, showing an increase of approximately 18.5% relative to the 'Upper Tubular' segment. The difference in mean C2M distance between the 'Lower Tubular' and 'LES Region' was minimal, with the two distal segments exhibiting a comparable magnitude of geometric deviation from the CT ground truth. In summary, this analysis identifies a clear spatial pattern in the reconstruction error for the TBE-only cohort, where geometric accuracy is highest in the proximal esophagus and systematically lower in the distal parts of the reconstructed models.

5 Discussion

This study undertook a formal validation of the *EsophagusVisualization* software, a multi-modal tool for the 3D reconstruction of the esophagus in patients with achalasia. By quantitatively and qualitatively comparing software-generated models against a high-fidelity ground truth derived from CT, this investigation sought to answer the central research question: To what degree of geometric and volumetric accuracy can the multi-modal software *EsophagusVisualization* reconstruct the 3D anatomy of the achalasia esophagus when compared against high-fidelity anatomical models derived from patients CT scans? The findings demonstrate that the software is capable of producing reconstructions with a high, clinically relevant degree of accuracy, particularly when a full complement of multi-modal data is available. However, the study also reveals specific limitations and systematic discrepancies that are dependent on the input data, the interpretation of which provides critical insights into both the software’s current capabilities and the biophysical realities of esophageal imaging. The principal findings of this investigation are as follows:

- 1. Superiority of Multi-Modal Reconstruction with EGD Data:** The most salient finding of this study is the profound impact of input data modality on reconstruction fidelity. The analysis of Patient 1, whose dataset uniquely included EGD data, yielded a model of exceptional accuracy. With a mean geometric C2M distance of 0.293 cm and a volumetric difference of less than 10 cm³, this multi-modal reconstruction significantly outperformed all models based solely on TBE data. This strongly suggests that the provision of direct cross-sectional luminal information from EGD acts as a powerful constraint on the reconstruction algorithm. It mitigates the geometric ambiguity inherent in inferring a 3D shape from a 2D projection, enabling the software to capture not only the overall morphology but also the volumetric properties of the esophagus with high precision. This result affirms that, under optimal data conditions, the software can achieve a very high degree of anatomical accuracy.
- 2. Systematic Discrepancies in TBE-Only Reconstruction Mode:** In contrast to the multi-modal case, the evaluation of the TBE-only cohort (Patients 2-6) revealed lower and more variable geometric accuracy. More significantly, this mode was associated with systematic discrepancies in volumetric assessment. The software’s reliance on a circular cross-section assumption in the absence of EGD data is the most probable cause of this limitation. The native esophagus, particularly when imaged via CT in a supine position, is often partially collapsed and assumes a non-circular lumen. The software’s algorithm, by extrapolating a 3D volume from the maximal width on a 2D TBE projection and assuming a circular shape, can lead to an over- or underestimation of the true volume. This highlights a key area for algorithmic improvement but also underscores the significant value gained by incorporating EGD data whenever possible.
- 3. Clinical Relevance of Achieved Geometric Accuracy:** A crucial aspect of this

validation is contextualizing the software’s performance within clinical standards. The optimal reconstructions frequently yielded mean C2M distances below 0.5 cm. This 5 mm threshold is not arbitrary; it is a well-established value in related clinical domains, particularly in radiotherapy planning for esophageal cancer, where geometric precision is paramount [42, 45] [43, 943]. For instance, standard clinical target volume expansions add a 0.5 cm margin to the gross tumor volume to account for microscopic spread [42, 45]. Furthermore, studies on inter-observer variability in manual esophageal contouring have reported standard deviations greater than 5 mm, especially in the longitudinal direction [43, 943]. That the software’s geometric error is on par with, or less than, the variability between human experts and within the range of standard clinical margins provides a strong argument for its clinical acceptability and potential utility in applications requiring high spatial fidelity.

4. **The Explanatory Power of Patient Positioning and Gravity:** A critical insight, informed by clinical consultation, is the role of patient positioning in explaining the observed discrepancies. TBE studies are performed with the patient in an upright posture, while CT scans are acquired in a supine position. The force of gravity acting on the dense barium contrast agent in the upright TBE posture naturally leads to greater distension of the dependent, distal portions of the esophagus. This biophysical difference provides a compelling explanation for the finding in Section 4.4, which demonstrated that geometric error was highest in the ‘Lower Tubular’ and ‘LES Region’. The greatest geometric discrepancy between the TBE-based model and the CT-based ground truth occurs precisely where the physical conditions of the imaging modalities differ the most. This finding elegantly explains the regional error distribution and suggests that the observed discrepancies are not merely software artifacts but reflect true physical differences between the two imaging states.
5. **Influence of TBE Acquisition Timing on Reconstruction Fidelity:** A consistent trend observed across the TBE-only cohort was that reconstructions derived from later TBE time points (typically 5 minutes) generally yielded higher geometric and volumetric accuracy than those from the initial 1-minute image. This can be attributed to the dynamics of contrast transit. At 1 minute, the esophagus is maximally distended with the barium bolus. At 2 and 5 minutes, partial outflow has occurred, leading to a less distended state that may be more representative of the esophagus’s baseline dilated morphology in achalasia. This suggests that for TBE-only reconstructions, utilizing later-phase images may provide a more reliable anatomical template, a finding that has direct implications for standardizing future data acquisition protocols for this software.
6. **Confirmed Internal Validity of the Software’s Volume Calculation:** A cornerstone of this study’s methodological rigor is the internal validation of the software’s own volumetric computation algorithm. The analysis in Section 4.3 demonstrated an exceptionally high correlation ($R^2 = 0.9925$ with $p < 0.001$) between the software’s internally reported volumes and those calculated by a

trusted external tool (Blender). This confirms that the software’s measurement capabilities are accurate and reliable relative to the models it generates. This finding is crucial, as it allows to conclude with confidence that the volumetric discrepancies observed between the software models and the CT ground truth are the result of genuine differences in the reconstructed shapes, stemming from different input data and imaging conditions, rather than any flaw or bug in the software’s internal measurement code.

This study, while comprehensive, has several limitations that must be acknowledged. The cohort size of six patients is small and limits the statistical power and generalizability of the findings. The heterogeneity of the data sources, with one intensively documented clinical case and five from a public repository, also presents challenges for direct comparison. Finally, the current workflow requires a manual post-processing step in Blender to correct mesh artifacts, which is a significant barrier to streamlined clinical adoption.

Future work should focus on addressing these limitations and enhancing the software’s capabilities. A primary goal should be the refinement of the TBE-only reconstruction algorithm to better approximate non-circular esophageal cross-sections, perhaps by incorporating statistical shape models or machine learning approaches trained on paired CT-TBE or EGD-TBE datasets. Furthermore, integrating additional data modalities could prove highly beneficial. The incorporation of data from the EndoFLIP™ impedance planimetry system, which provides direct measurements of luminal cross-sectional area and distensibility, could offer a powerful method for constraining the model’s geometry and adding a critical functional dimension. Lastly, the software’s export functionality must be improved to eliminate the need for external post-processing. This could be achieved by implementing more robust mesh generation algorithms that produce topologically clean and watertight models directly, or by integrating automated mesh-healing functions into the export pipeline to repair artifacts such as holes and non-manifold edges before the final file is written. Addressing these areas will be crucial for transitioning this promising visualization tool from a research prototype to a robust clinical instrument.

6 Conclusion

This study provides the first quantitative validation of the *Esophagus Visualization* software, confirming its capacity to generate patient-specific, three-dimensional models of the achalasic esophagus with clinically relevant accuracy. The highest accuracy was achieved through multi-modal reconstruction incorporating TBE, HRM, and EGD data, which yielded a mean geometric deviation of 0.293 cm and a volumetric difference under 10 cm³ compared to the CT-derived ground truth. This underscores the value of direct cross-sectional data from EGD in producing precise anatomical models. Reconstructions based solely on TBE data showed greater variability, with most models remaining within a clinically acceptable 0.5 cm mean deviation threshold. Systematic discrepancies, particularly in distal esophageal regions, were identified and attributed to biophysical differences between imaging postures (upright TBE vs. supine CT) rather than software error. The software’s internal volume calculation was validated as highly accurate

($R^2 = 0.9925$ with $p < 0.001$), confirming that observed volumetric differences stem from genuine shape incongruities.

While limitations such as a small cohort and manual post-processing exist, this work establishes a robust performance baseline for the software. Ultimately, *Esophagus Visualization* represents a significant advancement toward integrated, holistic assessment of achalasia by bridging the chasm between fragmented diagnostic modalities and cohesive, patient-specific 3D insights. By providing clinicians with quantifiable visualizations of esophageal morphology and dynamics, it holds promise for refining therapeutic strategies such as POEM and advancing personalized medicine. As we navigate the evolving landscape of computational gastroenterology, this work contributes a foundational benchmark, inviting further interdisciplinary collaboration to realize the full potential of such tools in ameliorating the burdens of rare esophageal disorders. Moreover, the validated reconstructions can serve as ground truth for the next phase of the project, which involves developing a generative AI model for reconstructing the esophagus of achalasia patients using only EGD data.

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